

Attribute Towards Corporate Social Responsibility- Case Studies of India Carbon Ltd Budge and Pabitra Beverages, Joka

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ABSTRACT

The recent Companies Act of 2013 have laid stress on Corporate Social Responsibility in India. Each and every corporate sector is supposed to contribute 2% of the last three yearly turnover towards Corporate Social Responsibility.

Windsor 2001 article examined the future of Corporate Social Responsibility or the relationship between business and society in the long run. The researcher made an attempt to find out whether different corporate houses and society will come closer to each other in future and the changing phase of CSR.

Nigel Sarbutts, 2003, explored the way of doing CSR by small and medium sized companies.

The present researcher has made an attempt to analyze attributes of one medium and one small scale sector in the outskirts of Kolkata, in 2017 and 2019 respectively which is being shared before the readers.

KEYWORDS: Corporate Social Responsibility, Small and Medium Scale sectors, Companies Act 2013

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CASE STUDY OF INDIA CARBON LTD., BUDGE

India Carbon Ltd alters petroleum residue, a crude product into modified fuel for Aluminium industry. It has started the procedure of optimum utilization of fuel. The products it produce is used as raw material in National Aluminum company and Hindustan Aluminum company.

Observation inside the factory:

The internal marketing tools as safeguarding the internal employees like the workers is regularly done inside the plant, helmets are given to workers and visitors to avoid exposure to the excessive heat and other danger like the rays falling directly over their head.

Disputes settled inside the factory are recycled on a regular basis. A quality control unit is developed inside the belt.

A consistent procedure of modulation of residual gases is done, so that it does not harm the people around, including stakeholders and other nearby factories.

The Ganges water, popularly known as Bhagirathi Hooghly in this belt, is recycled regularly by India Carbon Ltd. The residual wastes are regularly cleaned by the factory.

The morale and mottos imbibed in the value added messages in each and every nook and corner of the industry. The

workers and management always shared a bond where each other's safety is given prime importance.

A kitchen garden for nourishment of the workers with its vegetables is developed outside the factory.

The company made a turnover of 550 million in the financial year 2016-17, from which we can safely state that it is a medium scale industry.

The company restricts itself to Green HRM policies where the recruitment, selection and training of man power is devoid of any ambiguity.

FINDINGS

1. Green HRM tools.
2. Continual recycling of residue-wastes.
3. Promote greenery within the physical boundary of the factory.
4. Talent management and its' endorsement.
5. Overall endorsement of CSR tools.

FACTORY II
PABITRA BEVERAGES CORPORATION, JOKA, WEST BENGAL

Combating the chief competitors, Pepsico and Coca Cola, this industry, being a small scale industry is doing well to endorse CSR tools and techniques.

OBSERVATION

Unlike many industries in India, this unit has a quality endorsement cell. This cell helps in ensuring whether quality drinking water is being distributed to the consumers. Personal sources are used to train people from nearby areas who become the labourers in the factory.

Ground water is being diminished fast because of the continuous drilling procedure being observed by the soft drinks and processed water factories. The pabitra beverages have taken measures so that the water flow is regulated on a continuous basis so that the whole of the ground water is not being depleted.

Green HRM tools in terms of training and development programmes are ensured in order to scalp out quality

performance from the personnel being hired, recruited, selected and retained in the Organization.

The procedure followed in the Organization is purely microbiological which suggests that chemical elements and harmful estrogens are not allowed to sprout inside the factory. The internal marketing procedure is excellent which ensures retention of manpower within the factory.

FINDINGS

1. Green and pollution free environment within the factory.
2. Microbiological reduction of microbes with minimal use of chemicals.
3. No instances of nepotisms and favoritism being detected.
4. Green system in recruitment drive and manpower.

Conclusion:

With the small and medium scale industries coming forward to solve the green issues, we shall have to encourage and study more and more of such industries in the days to come to reduce stress inflicted upon mother Earth.

